

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The Financial Challenges of Parents of a Child with Autism in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: A Qualitative Study

Biruk Befkadu, Margaret E. Adamek^{1*}, Debebe Ero²

¹Indiana University

²College of Social Sciences,
Addis Ababa University

Correspondence Biruk Befkadu,
Margaret E. Adamek¹

Corresponding Author:

birukeb@gmail.com

Received:

Revised:

Accepted:

Abstract

Little is known about the financial challenges of autism. This study looks into the financial challenges faced by parents of a child living with autism in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Twelve in-depth interviews and four key informant interviews were held with the professionals in Joy and Nehemiah Autism Centers. The participants were selected via the convenience sampling method. The data were transcribed and analyzed through thematic data analysis. All the participants underlined that caring for a child with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) requires extra cost, attention, and effort. Most of the participants complained about the financial burden in relation to the cost of fulfilling the basic needs (high cost of food and clothing), transportation, and medical expenses. The system has to proactively work to address the financial and other concerns of the parents. The service is limited and unsatisfactory compared to the need. On the service provision, the government should try and address the different unmet needs and challenges of these children and their parents by providing proper attention and financial support.

Keywords: Autism, Parents, Financial Challenges

This is an open-access article published by the [Journal of Social Sciences and Management](#), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited

1. Introduction

Autism is a developmental disorder characterized by difficulties with social interactions, social communications and an unusually restricted range of behaviors and interests (Agyekum, 2018). The economic impact of having a child with the disorder is enormous and families with autistic children often experience a strain on their financial resources (Benson & Karlof, 2009; Linares-Gonzalez, 2006; Rogers, 2008). Glendinning (1986) indicated, Most private health insurance plans do not cover all expenses related to therapy and treatment for children with autism, and the payment for office visits and medications often results in huge financial debt. In addition to therapy and medical expenses, there are added economic burdens such as for accessing specialized educational toys, equipment like weighted blankets and vests, and much more (Cited in Hailemichael, 2014, p. 23).

ASD is known to be a costly disorder (New Zealand Ministries of Health and Education, 2008). Autism can place financial strains on parents in several ways. According to Lavelle et al. (2014), the average annual medical expense for a child diagnosed with autism in 2011 was about \$3,020. This cost was 18% higher than for a child without a diagnosis of autism. The authors further stated the caregiver of a child with autism may face costly prescriptions, emergency room visits, physician office visits, as well as occupational, speech, and physical therapy.

Costs associated with having a child with autism are not only limited to the cost of interventions. Like other forms of childhood disability, parents of a child with autism often face greater outlays of time and money (Aadil, Unjum, Afifa, & Zahoor, 2014). Participation in an extracurricular activity for children with autism also puts additional costs on the family. Thus, caring for an autistic child requires more expense in the provision of care, special